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M1 Development Economics Thesis

**Determinants of female genital cutting: comparison of Egypt and Ethiopia from 2005
until 2016**

Abstract

This paper empirically investigates the determinants of female genital cutting between 2005 and 2016 in Egypt and Ethiopia. The practice is decreasing in these countries but remains very present despite the fact that it has been an internationally recognized human rights violation. It is interesting to target the determinants of this phenomenon in order to be able to fight against it. The empirical literature has shown different views about it. This paper used four databases from the Demographic Health Survey: in Egypt in 2008 and 2014 and in Ethiopia in 2005 and 2016. Using logit regression, the evidence is as follows. A woman who has been circumcised is more likely to want the practice to continue. Her level of education and that of her husband, whether she is employed or not, her residential environment, and her religion would also have an impact on her position. Regarding the age of the woman, we do not obtain satisfactory results and can therefore not conclude anything about it. Based on these findings and the existing literature, this paper proposes a number of policy recommendations to reduce FGC.

Keywords: Female Genital cutting, gender inequalities, Egypt, Ethiopia

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1. Introduction

Female genital mutilation or cutting (FGM/C) is still common in some countries of the world: according to the world health organization, more than 200 girls and women alive today have undergone this practice in 30 countries (in Africa, Middle East and Asia). More precisely, from 2004 until 2015, more than 70 percent of the women have been subject to that practice in 10 countries of Africa (such as Egypt, Burkina Faso, Ethiopia...), according to UNICEF. However, Female genital mutilation is an internationally recognized human rights violation. It is a tradition that reflects the gender inequalities embedded in societies and is an extreme form of violence against girls and women. Indeed, it is one of the practices that harm them: for example, according to UNICEF, in 2020, 1 in 5 women in the world were circumcised by a specialist and therefore in good conditions. That one risks severe bleeding and problems urinating, and later cysts, infections, as well as complications in childbirth and increased risk of newborn deaths. Added to that, the others run the risk of serious health problems; or even death because they can be excised with a razor, a knife... As a consequence, in 2020, a 14 years old Egyptian girl died while undergoing the procedure. Treatment of the health complications of FGM in 27 high prevalence countries is estimated to cost 1.4 billion USD per year and is projected to rise to 2.3 billion USD by 2047 if no action is taken, according to the World Health Organisation. However, societies seem to perpetuate as a result of expectations about others' behaviors and normative beliefs (Mackie 1996). Even if some economists explained that religious practice may play a role in the decision of being circumcised (Bibars 2001), others have shown that this is not the first explanatory factor (Platas 2020). What is nowadays sometimes normalized, would be the result of customs put in place by men to reduce the risk of extramarital relationships from women (Becker 2019). Today, mothers and families often support these practices out of a desire to coordinate their activities with others and often become invested in a belief system that can hurt their female children. Thus, in some parts of the world, FGM/C is nearly universal. For example, in Egypt, according to the Demographic and Health Surveys, in 2014, 92,3 percent of the women have been subject to FGC. Even if this percentage has decreased over the years - in 2020, 87% of women have undergone this practice in Egypt, according to UNICEF - excised women remain a large majority of the population. As a consequence, in those countries, the decision for mothers to circumcise their daughters seems almost logical. To better know how can we limit this destructive practice, it is imperative to find out what factors justify it. However, the authors do not seem to agree on the determinants of the latter. The religious factor is most often stated as the first determinant. Thus, some authors have shown that this practice is more widespread among Muslims than among Christians (Yount 2004), (Gillum 2013). However, in Ethiopia, a predominantly Catholic country, 70 percent of women are circumcised in 2015, according to UNICEF. These figures show us that other factors play part in the FGM/C decision.

2. Literature Review

Work on female circumcision began to emerge in the 1990s. Today, the majority of the works that deal with female genital cutting (FGM/C) are focused on African countries. They look for the determinants of it and conclude what can be the solutions to reduce it. Note that they all use Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data applied to the country they are targeting as part of their analysis, for the dependent variable, which is whether or not a woman has been circumcised.

In 28 countries where FGM/C is practiced, in 11 of those more than 70 percent of girls and women aged between 15 to 49 years have undergone FGM/C, between 2004 and 2015, according to Unicef. In order to find these determinants, different strategies are used. Some articles, thanks to OLS regressions - and DHS data-, focus on one country such as Egypt (92,3 percent of women who have undergone FGM/C) (Becker 2019), Nigeria (2 percent) (Johnson 2007) and Ethiopia (74 percent) (Tesfaye Setegn 2016). While others compare several countries such as Egypt, Burkina Faso, and Somalia (Denison 2012), thanks to an integrative evidence approach.

These articles are mostly focused on individual determinants of FGM/C. The findings are broadly the same: religion is the primary determinant. Belonging to a religious group that emphasizes FGM/C favors this act. For example, in Egypt, excision is decreasing more and more among Christians, who denounce this practice, while among Muslims, it is struggling to decrease (Yount 2004). To find this result, the author used logistic regression to estimate odds ratios and 95 percent confidence intervals (Christian vs. Muslim). To explain that, we know that one of the beliefs that motivates FGM/C, is that without doing it, the girls would lose their honor. A study of 13 African countries, using conditional logistic regressions, showed that circumcised women are 40 percent more likely to be married than uncircumcised women (Wagner 2011). It goes further in Sudan, where women must be circumcised in order to marry.

Parents could be seen as victims of this decision out of concern for their daughter's well-being. They cut their daughters so that they can be married, and they want their sons to marry a girl who has been excised so that they are not excluded from the community. In Sudan, for example, tribal facial scarring is denounced, unlike female circumcision. Tribal facial scarring is the practice of making marks on the face of tribal members. These marks give identity to the tribe and beauty to its women. Women that choose not to permanently scar themselves can face discrimination since they are considered to have abandoned their traditions. We can therefore compare these two practices, which both affect women's rights. If women choose not to be victims of these practices, they suffer similar consequences. However, only the tribal facial scarring is denounced because if women choose to renounce tribal facial scarring, they lose beauty. If they want to renounce excision, which is invisible, they lose their honor, which has much more serious consequences (Lightfoot-Klein 1989).

The second determinant - which follows from this one - are the traditions. It has been shown that immigrants to Boston who were in favor of female circumcision prior to their settlement changed their minds after it. This change would be directly related to this immigration, and

therefore caused by the change in norms (Shahawy 2019). The methodology of this article is special because the authors did a qualitative study consisting of individual interviews in Boston, Massachusetts, with immigrant women who experienced FGC themselves and immigrant men with a family members who had experienced FGC, to explore their views on the practice and the discourse surrounding it.

Finally, the patriarchal tendency motivates much of this practice. The will of men to reduce women's sexual pleasure, for example, is one of the reasons. In addition, recent work uses older facts to justify the prevalence of FGM/C. Thus, some practice as pastoralism is justified as having standardized the practice. Pastoralism is a form of animal husbandry where men are obligated to go away from the camp for a few weeks or months to feed their animals. During this time, they are not at the camp and don't know what is happening. Women could have relationships with other men and become pregnant. So their husband are never sure if they are a parent of the child or not, while the women are. The inequalities of certainty of paternity lead to FGM/C: thanks to this, they would not have a relationship without him, and thus, they are certain to be the father of the child (Becker 2019). To obtain this result, Becker did a simple OLS regression and then an IV estimation which confirm the results from the OLS regressions in terms of coefficient sign and statistical significance.

Slavery would also play a role in explaining FGM/C. Empirical evidence has been found that populations that have been historically victimized by the Red slave route would have a higher rate of FGM/C. In the slave era, female slaves were used as lovers. The use of FGM/C was seen as a way to limit their pregnancies (Eliana La Ferrara 2020). Since one of the determinants of FGM/C is tradition, these ancient factors have anchored this practice in the cultures. Today, it would even represent an "identity" of a culture, or a ritual, which makes it even more difficult to eradicate.

These determinants that we have just seen are not the only ones, but they are the ones targeted as having the greatest impact on practice. The sex of the first child, the level of education of the woman and her husband, or the age of the woman would have an impact. On an other side, thanks to multiple linear regressions, some authors found that a woman's opinion of the practice would depend primarily on whether or not she has been cut. They created independent variables based on the woman's ethnicity, activities taking place in their community, and modernization. This allowed them to create a model in which they analyzed the impact of these on whether or not a woman was cut (DHS data). They found that if a women is circumcised, she is more likely to support the practice, and if she is not, she support it less.

In addition, belonging to a group of uncircumcised women reduces support for the practice. Compared to this, the age and education level of the woman would have little impact (Freymeyer and Johnson (2007)). Results obtained suggest that modernization would not influence excision. In the literature, there are less but still some articles looking at the determinants of FGM/C at the country level. That would influence excision in the long run.

By using a series of bivariate linear regressions, some authors explore several macro-level country characteristics that may be associated with overall FGM/ C participation within a country. They conclude that population density, equality in access to education, efforts to

outlaw the practice, and political stability, could reduce FGM/C. However, economic development, regime type, and international pressure would not have an impact on the practice (Brian Engelsma 2020). Nevertheless, thanks to the estimation of equations by ordinary least squares (OLS), one study found that 85 percent of the relationship between a woman's FGC status and her support for FGC is due to individual and household factors, which limits the impact of determinants at the country level (Marc F Bellemare 2015). They did different equations: each of it allow them to quantify the contribution of each level of variation (individual, household...) to FGM/C persistence.

Identifying the determinants of FGM/C provides insight into how we can reduce this harmful practice for women. The long run health impacts are various and known: genital problems, infections, pain, and in the worst cases, death. Many pathologies remain poorly studied, despite the fact that FGM/C has been identified as a "harmful practice" by international organizations (such as WHO, UNICEF...). The most identified pathologies are the problems of sexual life during life, but there would be also consequences on the child. There are also debates that seek to prove that FGM/C has an impact on women's rights, but the lack of data on women's sexual lives makes this difficult. Moreover, the social and cultural impacts of this practice should not be overlooked. FGM/C would contribute to maintaining gender differences, to the detriment of women. This leads, in particular, to a decrease in employment opportunities for women. If they are circumcised, they may be under the yoke of their husbands, and thus their freedoms are restricted. If, on the contrary, they want to show their opposition to this practice by not being excised, they may be excluded from social, economic and political life (Wodon 2015). This impact on women's rights has economic consequences on their country. Thus, whether on a national or individual scale, it seems favorable to all to fight against female genital cutting. Since religion is one of the main factors of FGM/C, one of the solutions to reduce it would be for religious communities to denounce it through public statements. Indeed, public declarations that fight against FGM/C would be effective (Freymeyer and Johnson (2007)). This suggests the need for integrated societal development interventions, such as involving religious leaders to fight against that practice. If they make public statements to show the harms of FGM/C, then it would help to decrease it. In addition, stories that highlight this practice should be limited or eliminated. To counter this, it may be interesting to instead increase people's knowledge about it, by highlighting the fact that it stems from discriminatory practices, such as slavery. Moreover, since FGM/C is seen as a religious "ritual", it should be replaced by another ritual which, ideally, does not infringe on women's rights (La Ferrara et al. (2020)). On the other hand, according to some authors, since FGM/C is so deeply rooted in tradition, even religious instructions aimed at denouncing it would not be sufficient (Mackie (1996)) - based based on actions that have been tried in the past. In addition, it is necessary to target individuals and households rather than communities, as we have seen that 85 percent of the determinants are at the individual level.

3. Stylized facts:

This section overview provides an overview of the evolution of the main variable of interest in this paper across the years and the different regions. We are going to divide this section into different parts, according to the variable which interests us.

3.1. Dependent variable: the woman's opinion about FGM/C:

In this section, we will focus on the dependent variable of the model of this article, which is the woman's opinion about FGM/C. We took the DHS databases in Egypt in 2008 and 2014 and in Ethiopia in 2005 and 2016, which are the dates of interest.

In Figure 1, we can see women's opinions about circumcision, in percentage, on which we will rely in this part.

First of all, we are going to focus on Egypt. We notice that a majority of women want this practice to continue, both in 2008 and 2014 (around 60% in average). However, there is a 5% decrease in this rate from 2008 to 2014 (from over 62 to over 57%). On the other hand, the percentage of women who think this practice should stop increased by about 3% (from over 28 to over 31). The rate of women who do not have an opinion about this also increases from 9.14 to 10.9%.

Secondly, in Ethiopia, in 2005, less than two-thirds of women want this practice stopped, and more than three quarters in 2016. Thus, the percentage of women who want this practice stopped increased by about 14% (from 63.12 to 78.45%). Therefore, the percentage of women who think that FGM/C should continue is divided by two (from 31.37 to 16.32%), while that of women who do not know is divided by less than 5 (from 5.49 to 1.43%).

To compare women's opinions about FGM/C in these two countries, and its evolution, we note that twice as many Egyptian women in 2008 as Ethiopian women in 2005 want the practice to continue. More than twice as many Ethiopian women in 2008 are against FGM/C compared to Egyptian women in 2005. The trend is similar in both countries as women are less and less in favour of this practice over the years, but it is much stronger in Ethiopia: in 2016 less than a quarter of the population is in favour of this practice, while in Egypt more than half are. We also note that Egyptian women who do not know what to think about FGM/C are much more than Ethiopian women (double in 2008 and 2005, and ten times more in 2014 and 2016).

Figure 1: Distribution of women according to their opinion about circumcision – Egypt (2008, 2014) and Ethiopia (2005, 2016):

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Egypt (2008 and 2014), and in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

3.2. First independent variable: whether or not the woman has undergone FGC:

We will now focus on a dependent variable of the models, which is whether or not the woman underwent FGM/C. On Figure 2, is represented the percentage of women who has undergone, or not FGM/C, in Egypt and Ethiopia.

First of all, we note that in Egypt, in 2008, almost all women have been circumcised. This percentage decreased along the years of about 3% in 2014 (from 95.55 to 92.3%). The percentage of uncircumcised women, therefore, increases by about 3% (4,43 to 7,7%).

In Ethiopia, even if there is less women circumcised: in 2005 (74,26%) and in 2016 (70,37%), the trend is the same. We can see a decrease in the percentage of women cut by 4% (from more than 74% to more than 70%) from 2005 to 2016. The percentage of uncircumcised women has increased by more than 6%. The difference between these two variations is explained by the fact that in 2005, there is a percentage of women for whom no data is available of more than 2%.

To compare these variables in the two countries, we note that the percentage of circumcised women in Egypt is much higher than that of Ethiopian women (a difference of more than 20% in 2005 and 2008). However, the evolution is quite similar because, in both countries, we notice a decrease in this rate of more than 3%.

Figure 2: Distribution of women according to whether or not she has undergone this practice – Egypt (2008, 2014) and Ethiopia (2005, 2016):

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Egypt (2008 and 2014), and in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

3.3. Women's views on FGM/C and their education:

The graphs shown in this section in Figure 3 present the women's opinions on FGM/C depending on their education. On the top left the graph presents the opinion of Egyptian women wishing FGC to continue in 2008, and on the right in 2014, according to their maximum level of education. On the bottom left we find the opinion of Ethiopian women in 2005 and on the right in 2016, according to their highest level of education.

First of all, on the graph at the top left, which focuses on Egyptian women in 2008, we see that the less educated women are, the more they support this practice. Uneducated women are more than twice as supportive of the practice as women with more than high school education (respectively 76,1 and 32,1%). Thus, more than 60% of women with a level of education higher than secondary school think that FGM/C should be stopped, compared to 33,7% for those who have been to secondary school, 19,81% for those who have been to primary school, and 13,5% for those who are not educated, in 2008. The percentage of women who do not have an opinion about this practice also decreases with the level of education (from 10,39 to 6,9%).

In 2014 (the top right graphic), we note that the percentages of women who want FGC to continue are quite similar to those of 2008; with a slight decrease of 4% on average. However, the percentage of women with an education higher than high school who think that FGM/C should continue increases (from 32,14% to 35,48%). In addition, the number of women who do not have an opinion on whether or not FGM/C should continue has increased among women with primary, secondary, and higher education (from about 8% and 6% to 10%, respectively).

On the bottom graphics, we can focus on Ethiopia, there is also a negative correlation between a woman's opinion about FGM/C and her level of education. However, women who want FGM/C to stop are much more likely to be in the majority regardless of their level of education, whether in 2005 or 2016. In 2005 (bottom left), slightly more than the majority of

uneducated women wanted FGC stopped (52.01%), compared to almost all of those with secondary education or higher (more than 94%). This trend is increasing for all levels of education, except for those with secondary education, where the percentage is stagnant.

For these percentages in Ethiopia and Egypt, regardless of years and levels of education, Egyptian women are much more supportive of the continued practice than Ethiopian women. However, in both countries, there is a negative correlation between their opinion and their level of education (the more educative they are, the less they support that practice), and a decrease in the percentage of those wishing to continue the practice among the years.

Figure 3: Distribution of women depending on their opinion about FGC and their education– Egypt (2008, 2014) and Ethiopia (2005, 2016)

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Egypt (2008 and 2014), and in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

3.4. Women's opinions about FGC according to their type of residence:

We will now analyse the evolution of women's opinions about FGC according to their type of place of residence in Egypt (from 2008 to 2014) and Ethiopia (from 2005 to 2016), thanks to figure 4.

Frist of all, in Egypt (left graphic), in 2008, women living in rural areas were 20% more to be in favor of the continuation of the practice than those living in urban areas (around 50 to 70%). From 2008 to 2014, the trend of this percentage is decreasing in all areas, and therefore the percentage of women who want this practice to stop is increasing (around 3% for all areas).

We also note that those who do not have an opinion increased over the years (respectively an increase of 3 and 1%).

In Ethiopia (right graphic), regardless of the type of area and year, women who want to stop the practice (with a percentage between 57 when it is at its lowest and more than 90% at its maximum) to far outnumber those who want it to continue, with percentages far higher than those of Egyptian women. For example, in urban areas compared to 2005 and 2008, there is a 40% gap between Ethiopian and Egyptian women who want this practice to stop. In 2014 and 2016, in rural areas, there is a gap of more than 50%.

The evolution of Ethiopian women's opinions is similar to that of Egyptian women, with an increase in the number of women who think that FGM/C should be stopped, regardless of the area. The percentage of these increases on average by more than 3%, regardless of the area, year and country concerned. We note that the evolution of this percentage is stronger than the others in rural areas between 2005 and 2016 in Ethiopia, because there is a variation of just under 20%.

Figure 4: Distribution of women depending on their opinion about FGC and their type of residence – Egypt (2008, 2014) and Ethiopia (2005, 2016)

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Egypt (2008 and 2014), and in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

4. Data and methodology :

This paper empirically studies the determinants of FGM/C jointly in Egypt in 2004 and 2014; and in Ethiopia from 2006 to 2015. The used data is retrieved from the Democratic Health Survey (DHS) dataset. This follows the definition that female circumcision, also known as female genital mutilation (FGM) or female genital cutting (FGC), includes all procedures involving partial or total removal of the external female genitalia or other injury to the female sexual organs.

Female genital mutilation is classified into 4 types. The first type is the partial or total removal of the clitoral glans and/or the prepuce. The second type is the first type added to the removal of the labia minora and possibly the labia majora. The third type, also named infibulation is the narrowing of the vaginal opening through the creation of a covering seal. It can be made with

removal of the clitoral glans. To finish, the last type includes all other harmful procedures to the female genitalia for non-medical purpose.

It has been recognized that this practice has no health benefits, but can cause many health complications. The immediate complication can be excessive bleeding, urinary problems, injury to surrounding genital tissue, or death. The long-term complications are urinary, vaginal, menstrual, sexual, and psychological problems.

The data cover only women who are between 15 and 49 years of age, because excision is almost universally performed before the age of 15. Sample sizes range from 14070 (Ethiopia, 2005), to 28175 women (Egypt, 2014). This paper follows the econometric methodology applied by Blaydes and Platas (2020).

This paper analyses what are the determinants of FGM/C in Egypt, thanks to a logit regression. This means that the dependent variable is equal to 1 if the woman wants the practice to continue, and 0 otherwise (circont). It is the probability that a woman supports FGM/C. It permits to more easily use of the evolution of the woman's behavior over time. This allows us to realize that if the woman has been circumcised, does she support this practice or not, for example. We can also see the impact of her age and the environment in which she lives on her position regarding FGC.

Concerning the independent variables, we are going to use some determinants mentioned in the literature review which we have seen previously (Freymeyer and Johnson (2007); Mackie (1996...)).

The first and most important determinant, which is the first independent variable, is whether the woman is circumcised, which may explain why she supports, or not, this treatment. Indeed, if a woman is circumcised, she may be more likely to support the practice, whereas if she is not, she may be less likely to see its usefulness and see its negative impacts. This is also related to culture and traditions. If a woman has been circumcised, it means that it is required, or at least not questioned by her culture. It may be necessary for her to get married, to be cut, for example. So, if this is the case, she has no reason to want this practice to stop. This is incorporated into the model as a variable (circ) that equals 1 if the woman is circumcised and 0 otherwise.

Then, we will analyse whether the fact that the woman has a job or not has an impact on her opinion of this practice. We assume that if a woman does not have a job, she is more likely to tolerate the practice because those around her do not question it. On the other hand, if she has a job, she can discover new horizons, and meet new people who may tend to do it. The corresponding variable (nonwork) is equal to 1 if the woman has no job and 0 otherwise.

Since studies have shown that the age, education, and residence of the women have an impact on this practice, our model is going to explore the impact of it on FGM/C. Through that, our model will consider the impact of specific efforts that might change the social convention concerning circumcision. We expect women with more exposure to specific programs against FGM/C and to modern ideas, in general, to have less support for the practice.

Thus, the third regressor of the model in this article is the woman's living environment: does she live in an urban or rural area. It is assumed that this has an impact on her opinion on whether

or not to continue cutting. If a woman lives in a rural area, the traditions are more ingrained in her way of life. As traditions are a determinant of FGM/C, she is more likely to support it. On the other hand, in urban areas, people may be more likely to question it, because traditions are less entrenched and more questioned. The variable (*urb*) is therefore a variable that is equal to 1 if the woman lives in an urban area and 0 otherwise

The age of the woman is also seen as having an impact on the woman's opinion about FGC in the existing literature. An older woman is more likely to support it, as it is more rooted in their traditions and less questioned. Today, the practice is being questioned, and younger women may be more aware of its limitations. For this factor, dummy variables were created for each age group (15-19 years, 20-24 years, etc.). The reference variable corresponds to women between 15 and 19 years old. Thus, variables corresponding to the other age groups (women between 20 and 24 years old: *age_1*, up to those between 45 and 49 years old: *age_7*) are included in the model. The coefficient obtained will be used to compare the opinions of women in the age group of interest with those aged between 15 and 19.

Next, we will add a variable concerning the level of education of the wife, and of her husband. We suppose that the more educated the woman is, the less she will support this practice. Indeed, thanks to her education, she will have the capacity to inform herself about this subject, meet new people, a new environment. She will have more strength to learn about the limits of this practice, and to dare to assert herself against her family and traditions. The same goes for her husband. And, it is assumed, that if her husband questions this practice, the woman will be more likely to do so. Dummy variables will also be created in both cases, with the reference variable corresponding to women (*educw_*) and men (*educm_*) who have no education respectively.

The last explanatory variable will be different for Egypt and Ethiopia, as we will describe below.

4.1. Egypt :

The model concerning Egypt focuses on the year 2008 and 2014.

It will take the form that has been presented previously, adding a regressor concerning the governorate of habitat of the woman. Dummy variables have also been created, with the reference variable corresponding to women living in the governorate of Cairo. Thus, for example, the variable *govern_2* corresponds to women living in the governorate of Alexandria.

$$P(circcont)_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 circ_{it} + \beta_2 nonwork_{it} + \beta_3 urb_{it} + \beta_4 age_2 + \beta_5 age_3 + \dots + \beta_9 age_7 + \beta_{10} educw_2 + \dots + \beta_{13} educw_4 + \beta_{15} edum_2 + \dots + \beta_{21} edum_7 + \beta_{22} govern_2 + \dots + \beta_{48} govern_{27} + \dots + \beta_{49} X_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

For women *i* surveyed at date *t*

This model includes dummy variables:

- $Circ_{it} = 1$ if the mother has undergone this practice, 0 otherwise;
- $Nonwork_{it}=1$ if the women doesn't have a job, 0 otherwise;
- $Urb_{it}=1$ if the women lives in urban area, 0 otherwise;
- $Age_2_{it}=1$ if the women is between 20 and 24 years old, 0 otherwise;
- $Eduw_2_{it}=1$ if the women has a maximum education level of elementary school;
- $Edum_2_{it}=1$ if the husband has a maximum education level of elementary school;
- $Govern_2_{it}=1$ if the women lives in Alexandria governorate

4.2. Ethiopia:

About Ethiopia, the same regression as Egypt will be performed but for different dates: 2005 and 2016, to be able to compare these two countries and notably the impact of religion on FGC.

Performing this regression on the case of Ethiopia makes it possible to analyze the impact of religion on women's position on FGC. In Egypt, more than 90% of women are Muslims, so it is difficult to identify the impact of religion on the practice. In Ethiopia, on the other hand, there is not really a dominant religion. More than 60% of Ethiopians are Christians (43% Orthodox, 18% Protestant, 0.7% Catholic); more than 30% are Muslims, and about 3% are traditional religions. We assume that Muslim women will be more likely to endure this practice, knowing that the countries with the highest rates of female circumcision are Muslim majority countries. Ethiopia is one of the exceptions.

For the religion variable ($relig_$), dummy variables will be included. The reference variable refers to women with the religion "other".

$$P(circcont)_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 circ_{it} + \beta_2 nonwork_{it} + \beta_3 urb_{it} + \beta_4 age_2 + \beta_5 age_3 + \dots + \beta_9 age_7 + \beta_{10} eduw_2 + \dots + \beta_{13} eduw_4 + \beta_{15} edum_2 + \dots + \beta_{21} edum_7 + \beta_{22} relig_1 + \dots + \beta_{25} relig_5 + \dots + \beta_{26} X_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

For women i surveyed at date t

This model includes dummy variables:

- $Circ_{it} = 1$ if the mother has undergone this practice, 0 otherwise;
- $Nonwork_{it}=1$ if the women doesn't have a job, 0 otherwise;
- $Urb_{it}=1$ if the women lives in urban area, 0 otherwise;
- $Age_2_{it}=1$ if the women is between 20 and 24 years old, 0 otherwise;
- $Eduw_2_{it}=1$ if the women has a maximum education level of elementary school;
- $Edum_2_{it}=1$ if the husband has a maximum education level of elementary school;

- $Relig_1_{it}=1$ if the women if it is of protestant religion, 0 otherwise

4.3. Ethiopia and Egypt merged:

In the last model, Ethiopia and Egypt will be combined into one model. This will allow us to analyse the impact of the year in which the woman was interviewed, and her country of residence on her position about FGM/C. The goal is also to identify the impact of the country's culture and traditions on FGM/C. It also allow us to see if over the years women are becoming more or less supportive of this practice.

The model is of the same form as the previous models (logit model), and includes the dependent variables common to the previous models.

However, the regressors are different. A variable has been added for the reference country (Egypt). It is equal to 1 if the country concerned is Egypt, and 0 otherwise. This variable should allow us to identify whether the culture of Egypt is more conducive to perpetuating the practice than that of Ethiopia, or not. We assume that the Egyptian culture and traditions favor the prosperity of this practice. In the "stylized facts" section, we notice that Egyptian women want this tradition to continue more than Ethiopian women.

The variable year, is a variable equal to 1 if the year concerned is less than 2010 and 0 otherwise. This will allow us to know if before 2010, women are more willing to continue the practice, compared to after 2010. It is assumed that before 2010, women think more that this practice should continue, compared to after 2010. Indeed, over time, traditions change. FGC is an ancient cultural tradition that is increasingly denounced over time.

$$P(circcont)_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 Egypt_{it} + \beta_2 Year2010_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

This model includes dummy variables:

- $Egypt_{it}=1$ if the women lives in Egypt, 0 otherwise
- $Year2010_{it}=1$ if the woman was interviewed before 2010, 0 otherwise

5. Empirical Results:

This section presents the results of the different estimated versions of the models. As explained in the methodology section, our goal is to measure the determinants of FGC. To do this, we look at the factors that impact a woman's position on FGC. This will allow us to validate or not the determinants identified in the existing literature. The different models are logit models, where the dependent variable is equal to 1 if the woman thinks that FGC should continue, and 0 otherwise.

5.1. Egypt 2008:

The first model targeted women in Egypt in 2008. The results obtained are shown in table 1.

It seems that when a woman has been circumcised, the likelihood that she wants the practice to continue increases by 267 percentage points.

The correlation between a woman not having a job and wanting the practice to continue is also positive. Thus, if a woman does not have a job, the probability that she will support the practice increases by 16.7 percentage points, on average, all else being equal.

There is a negative correlation between the fact that the woman wants this practice to continue and the fact that she lives in an urban area. It seems that the probability that a woman living in an urban area will support this practice is 45.6 percentage points lower than if she lives in a rural area, on average.

We see that for each age range, the probability that the woman supports is higher than that of our reference variable. For example, if a woman is between 29 and 34 years of age, the probability that she will support the continuation of FGC increases by 27.4 percentage points, on average. We see that the women who are most likely to support this practice are those between 35 and 39 years of age, because their coefficient is higher. On average, the probability that women between 35 and 39 years of age support the continuation of FGC increases by 35.6 percentage points. We note that, overall, all else being equal, older women are more likely to support the continuation of this practice than younger women.

We note that the probability that the woman will support this practice decreases with her level of education (the coefficient decreases with the level of education). For example, the probability that women with a university education support the practice decreases by 124 percentage points, on average.

As for women, the probability that the man will support this practice decreases with his level of education. Thus, the probability that a woman with a husband who has a higher education level than university will support the practice increases by 54.9 percentage points, on average.

We notice that in the majority of governorates, the probability that the woman supports this practice is higher than those living in the governorate of Cairo (except in the governorate of Port Said, or Matruh for example). For example, if a woman lives in Beheira governorate, the probability that she will support the practice increases by 106 percentage points. On the other hand, there are some exceptions, such as women living in the governorate of Port Said. A woman residing in this governorate is 78 percentage points less likely than a woman living in the governorate of Cairo to support the practice.

Finally, we notice that some variables are not significant. That means that we can't estimate the impact of between 20 and 24 years old, or women residing in the governorate of Alexandria, for example.

In this regression, the Pseudo R square is equal to 0.16, which means that the model explains 16% of the variation in the dependant variable. This is quite low, but this is explained by the fact that this is a logit regression.

Table 1 – Logit model: Egypt 2008

Logistic regression							
circcont	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
circ	2.675	.147	18.21	0	2.387	2.962	***
nonwork	.167	.052	3.22	.001	.065	.269	***
urb	-.456	.045	-10.17	0	-.544	-.368	***
age_2	.081	.099	0.82	.414	-.113	.275	
age_3	.145	.098	1.48	.138	-.047	.336	
age_4	.274	.1	2.73	.006	.077	.47	***
age_5	.358	.102	3.52	0	.159	.558	***
age_6	.356	.104	3.43	.001	.153	.559	***
age_7	.29	.106	2.74	.006	.083	.497	***
educw_2	-.154	.065	-2.35	.019	-.282	-.026	**
educw_3	-.681	.055	-12.34	0	-.789	-.573	***
educw_4	-1.238	.088	-14.10	0	-1.41	-1.066	***
educm_2	-.091	.063	-1.44	.151	-.215	.033	
educm_3	-.128	.075	-1.70	.089	-.276	.019	*
educm_4	-.178	.061	-2.92	.004	-.298	-.058	***
educm_5	-.34	.103	-3.31	.001	-.541	-.139	***
educm_6	-.392	.08	-4.93	0	-.548	-.236	***
educm_7	-.549	.243	-2.26	.024	-1.025	-.074	**
govern_2	-.279	.1	-2.78	.005	-.476	-.083	***
govern_3	-.757	.133	-5.69	0	-1.018	-.497	***
govern_4	.96	.132	7.28	0	.701	1.219	***
govern_5	-.973	.119	-8.16	0	-1.207	-.74	***
govern_6	.883	.106	8.34	0	.675	1.09	***
govern_7	.755	.099	7.63	0	.561	.949	***
govern_8	.22	.092	2.39	.017	.04	.401	**
govern_9	.183	.108	1.70	.089	-.028	.394	*
govern_10	.258	.099	2.62	.009	.065	.452	***
govern_11	.62	.109	5.66	0	.406	.835	***
govern_12	-1.158	.091	-12.78	0	-1.336	-.98	***
govern_13	.247	.121	2.04	.041	.01	.483	**
govern_14	.381	.097	3.92	0	.19	.571	***
govern_15	.284	.101	2.82	.005	.087	.482	***
govern_16	.136	.107	1.28	.202	-.073	.346	
govern_17	-.467	.092	-5.07	0	-.648	-.287	***
govern_18	-.358	.092	-3.89	0	-.539	-.178	***
govern_19	.172	.093	1.84	.065	-.011	.355	*
govern_21	1.059	.133	7.97	0	.799	1.32	***
govern_22	.948	.137	6.90	0	.679	1.217	***
govern_23	.19	.176	1.08	.282	-.156	.535	
govern_24	.546	.19	2.88	.004	.175	.918	***
govern_25	-1.243	.208	-5.97	0	-1.651	-.835	***
govern_26	.033	.177	0.19	.851	-.313	.379	
govern_27	.591	.259	2.28	.022	.084	1.099	**
Constant	-1.682	.192	-8.74	0	-2.059	-1.305	***
Mean dependent var		0.623	SD dependent var			0.485	
Pseudo r-squared		0.160	Number of obs			16527	
Chi-square		3513.258	Prob > chi2			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		18479.877	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			18819.238	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

5.2. Egypt 2014 :

This second model has the same form as the previous regression. The results obtained are presented in Table 2.

The coefficients are all of the same sign as in table 1, but the coefficients vary, so we can now make comparisons.

We note that the probability that a women who has undergone the practice decrease by 50 percentage points. Which means that circumcised women are less likely to want the practice to continue, compared to 2008.

We notice that this variable associated with the fact that the women doesn't have a job is not significant, so we cannot interpret it.

The probability that a woman living in an urban area will support this practice is 7.4 percentage points lower than if she lives in a rural area. It can be seen that this probability is lower than in 2008. This means that there is more gap in position between women living in rural areas and those living in urban areas. Thus, either woman living in urban areas are less likely to support this practice, or those living in rural areas are more likely to support it.

Regarding age, we see that for each age group, the variables are not significant and we can therefore conclude nothing.

The probability that women with a university education will support the practice increases by 105 percentage points, on average. This figure has decreased by 20 percentage points compared to 2008, meaning that there is less of a gap between educated and uneducated women about whether they support the practice or not.

As for women, the probability that the man will support this practice decreases with his level of education. For example, the probability that a woman with a husband who has a level of education higher than university supports the practice increases by 24.9 percentage points, on average. There is also a decrease of more than 20 percentage points compared to 2008.

We notice that in the majority of governorates, the probability that the woman supports this practice is higher than those living in the governorate of Cairo (except in the governorate of port said, or menya for example). For example, if a woman lives in this Beheira governorate, the probability that she will support the practice increases by 48 percentage points, on average, in comparison with a woman living in the Cairo governorate. This coefficient decreased by almost 50 percentage points compared to 2008. This means that either women living in Cairo Governorate are more interested in continuing FGC, or those living in Beheira Governorate are much more opposed to it.

On the other hand, there are some exceptions, such as for women residing in the governorate of Port Said. A woman living in this governorate is 101 percentage points less likely than a woman living in Cairo governorate to support the practice. This figure increases by 30 percentage points

in comparison to 2008, which means that there is a greater thought gap between women living in these two governorates.

What we can conclude from this is that either women living in Cairo governorate support this practice more, or those living in the governorates we are interested in today support this practice much less.

In this regression, the pseudo R square is equal to 0.197, which means that the model explains 19.7% of the variation in the dependant variable. This R2 is higher than the R2 of the previous regression, which means that the dependent variables explain more of the variation in the independent variable.

Table 2 - Logit model : Egypte 2014 :

Logistic regression							
circcont	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
circ	2.188	.085	25.72	0	2.021	2.354	***
nonwork	-.053	.045	-1.18	.238	-.141	.035	
urb	-.737	.038	-19.36	0	-.812	-.663	***
age_2	-.082	.098	-0.84	.4	-.274	.109	
age_3	-.123	.095	-1.30	.194	-.309	.063	
age_4	-.064	.096	-0.67	.502	-.252	.124	
age_5	-.004	.098	-0.04	.968	-.195	.187	
age_6	-.035	.1	-0.36	.722	-.231	.16	
age_7	-.094	.101	-0.93	.351	-.293	.104	
educw_2	-.114	.064	-1.78	.075	-.239	.011	*
educw_3	-.56	.05	-11.27	0	-.657	-.462	***
educw_4	-1.055	.073	-14.39	0	-1.199	-.912	***
educm_2	-.017	.061	-0.29	.775	-.136	.101	
educm_3	-.105	.067	-1.55	.12	-.237	.027	
educm_4	-.169	.054	-3.13	.002	-.274	-.063	***
educm_5	-.234	.092	-2.55	.011	-.414	-.054	**
educm_6	-.336	.07	-4.82	0	-.473	-.199	***
educm_7	-.249	.215	-1.16	.247	-.671	.173	
govern_2	-1.058	.099	-10.68	0	-1.252	-.864	***
govern_3	-1.01	.098	-10.29	0	-1.203	-.818	***
govern_4	-.704	.087	-8.07	0	-.875	-.533	***
govern_5	-2.443	.104	-23.50	0	-2.647	-2.239	***
govern_6	-.997	.086	-11.60	0	-1.165	-.828	***
govern_7	.19	.092	2.06	.039	.009	.37	**
govern_8	-.172	.09	-1.91	.056	-.348	.004	*
govern_9	-.628	.088	-7.17	0	-.8	-.456	***
govern_10	-.866	.089	-9.71	0	-1.041	-.691	***
govern_11	-.505	.091	-5.55	0	-.683	-.327	***
govern_12	-1.492	.084	-17.84	0	-1.656	-1.328	***
govern_13	-.677	.089	-7.63	0	-.851	-.503	***
govern_14	-.461	.082	-5.62	0	-.622	-.3	***
govern_15	-.073	.095	-0.78	.438	-.259	.112	
govern_16	-.302	.095	-3.17	.002	-.489	-.115	***
govern_17	-.715	.091	-7.88	0	-.893	-.537	***
govern_18	-.338	.089	-3.80	0	-.512	-.164	***
govern_19	-.465	.09	-5.16	0	-.641	-.288	***
govern_21	.487	.099	4.92	0	.293	.681	***
govern_22	.9	.108	8.32	0	.688	1.112	***
govern_23	-.479	.121	-3.97	0	-.716	-.243	***
govern_24	.804	.132	6.09	0	.545	1.063	***
govern_25	-2.58	.228	-11.30	0	-3.028	-2.133	***
Constant	-.194	.145	-1.34	.182	-.478	.09	

Mean dependent var	0.559	SD dependent var	0.497
Pseudo r-squared	0.197	Number of obs	21760
Chi-square	5868.633	Prob > chi2	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	24076.889	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	24412.377

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

5.3. Ethiopia 2005 :

The models for Ethiopia in 2005 are different because there is no data on the governorates of residence of the women, but a variable on religion has been added to analyse the impact of religion on women's position on FGC. The results are shown in Table 4.

When a woman is circumcised, the probability that she wants the practice of FGC to continue increases by 203 percentage points. This is 67 percentage points less than in Egypt in 2008: circumcised women in Ethiopia are less likely to want the practice to continue than those in Egypt, all else being equal.

There is therefore a negative correlation between the fact that the woman wants this practice to continue and the fact that she lives in an urban area. This means that the probability that a woman living in an urban area will support this practice is 90.3 percentage points lower than if she lives in a rural area. There is an increase of 50 percentage points compared to Egyptian women in 2008. This means that there is less of a difference in position about whether or not they continue to practice this practice between Egyptian women living in urban and rural areas than Ethiopian women.

Regarding age, we notice that only the variable associated with women between 35 and 39 and the one of women aged between 40 and 45 are significant. We note that overall, older women are less likely to support the continuation of this practice than younger women. Moreover, on average, the probability that women aged 35 to 39 support the continuation of FGC decreases by 28,4 percentage points. This result is surprising because it means that younger women tolerate this practice more than older women. If we analyze the database, we can see that this is due to the fact that women between 15 and 19 years of age are three times more than those between 39 and 45 years of age, for example (3 thousand versus 1 thousand). Table 5 in the appendix shows that the percentage of women between 15 and 19 who want FGC to continue is lower than that of women between 45 and 49 (20 versus 31 percent).

We note that the probability that the woman will support this practice decreases with her level of education (the coefficient decreases with the level of education). For example, the probability that women with a university education support the practice increases by 185 percentage points, on average. We note that this figure is about 60 percentage points higher compared to Egyptian women in 2008: in Ethiopia, the level of education determines more the opinion of the woman on her willingness to continue the practice or not.

As for women, the probability that the man will support this practice decreases with his level of education. The probability that a woman with a husband who has an education level higher

than university will support the practice increases by 120 percentage points, on average. This is higher than that of Egyptian women.

Finally, about religion, only the variable that corresponds to women being Muslim is significant. The probability that a Muslim woman supports this practice increases by 90.7 percent in comparison with a woman of the "other" religion.

In this regression, the Pseudo R square is equal to 0.192, which means that the model explain 19.1% of the variation in the dependant variable. This R2 is approximately equal to the previous one.

Table 3- Logit model : Ethiopia 2005

Logistic regression							
circont	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
circ	2.036	.083	24.63	0	1.874	2.198	***
nonwork	-.046	.471	-0.10	.922	-.97	.878	
urb	-.903	.082	-11.00	0	-1.064	-.742	***
age_2	-.105	.102	-1.03	.303	-.306	.095	
age_3	.03	.098	0.30	.762	-.162	.221	
age_4	.026	.102	0.25	.799	-.174	.226	
age_5	-.125	.103	-1.22	.224	-.328	.077	
age_6	-.284	.11	-2.59	.009	-.499	-.07	***
age_7	-.23	.111	-2.07	.039	-.448	-.012	**
educw_2	-.453	.077	-5.86	0	-.605	-.302	***
educw_3	-1.244	.168	-7.39	0	-1.575	-.914	***
educw_4	-1.869	.668	-2.80	.005	-3.179	-.559	***
educm_2	-.501	.063	-7.94	0	-.625	-.378	***
educm_3	-.613	.103	-5.98	0	-.814	-.412	***
educm_4	-1.206	.331	-3.65	0	-1.854	-.557	***
educm_5	-.261	.388	-0.67	.501	-1.021	.499	
educm_6	-.753	.45	-1.67	.094	-1.635	.129	*
relig_1	.503	.271	1.86	.063	-.027	1.033	*
relig_2	.109	.381	0.29	.775	-.639	.857	
relig_3	.035	.277	0.13	.9	-.508	.578	
relig_4	.907	.27	3.35	.001	.377	1.436	***
relig_5	-.166	.383	-0.43	.666	-.917	.586	
Constant	-2.465	.287	-8.60	0	-3.026	-1.903	***
Mean dependent var		0.312	SD dependent var			0.463	
Pseudo r-squared		0.192	Number of obs			10240	
Chi-square		2437.219	Prob > chi2			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		10327.053	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			10493.436	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

5.4. Ethiopia 2016 :

This model focuses on Ethiopia in 2016. The results obtained are presented in Table 4.

When the woman is excised, the probability that she wants the practice of excision to continue increases by 392 percentage points, on average. This coefficient doubles between 2005 and

2016, which means that circumcised women are more likely to want the practice to continue compared to uncircumcised women.

If a woman does not have a job, the probability that she will support the practice increases by 21.2 percentage points, on average. This is 5 percentage points higher than in 2005, so women who do not have a job in Ethiopia want this practice to continue more, compared to women who have a job, compared to 2016.

The probability that a woman living in an urban area will support this practice is 51.7 percentage points lower than if she lives in a rural area. There is an increase of more than 10 percentage points compared to Egyptian women in 2008. This means that there is a bigger difference in the position about the continuity of this practice or not between Ethiopian women living in urban and rural areas.

We note that overall, older women are less likely to support the continuation of this practice than younger women. On average, the probability that women aged 35 to 39 support the continuation of FGC decreases by 65,7 percentage points.

We notice that the probability that the woman supports this practice decreases with her level of education (the coefficient decreases with the level of education). For example, the probability that women with a university education support the practice increases by 133 percentage points, on average. We note that this figure is about 50 percentage points lower than in 2005: in 2016, the level of education determines less the opinion of the woman on her willingness to continue or not to perform FGC, compared to 2005.

The probability that a woman with a husband who has an education level higher than university will support the practice decreases by 65.7 percentage points, on average.

Finally, the variable is the variable that corresponds to the woman's religion. We also created dummy variables, and put in reference religion the "other" religion (women who are not Protestant, Orthodox or Muslim). None of these variables are significant, so we cannot conclude anything.

In this regression, the R square is equal to 0.3772, which means that the dependent variables explain 37.7% of the variation in the model. This R2 is double that of previous regressions, which means that the independent variables determine more of the variation of the independent variables.

Table 4- Logit model : Ethiopia 2005 :

Logistic regression							
circont	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
circ	3.921	.144	27.30	0	3.64	4.203	***
nonwork	.212	.083	2.56	.011	.049	.375	**
urb	-.517	.121	-4.29	0	-.754	-.281	***
age_2	-.225	.168	-1.34	.181	-.555	.105	
age_3	-.515	.167	-3.09	.002	-.841	-.188	***
age_4	-.812	.173	-4.69	0	-1.151	-.472	***
age_5	-.721	.176	-4.09	0	-1.066	-.375	***
age_6	-.78	.191	-4.08	0	-1.154	-.406	***

age_7	-0.657	.203	-3.23	.001	-1.055	-.259	***
educw_2	-.628	.106	-5.90	0	-.836	-.419	***
educw_3	-1.514	.258	-5.88	0	-2.019	-1.009	***
educw_4	-1.333	.37	-3.60	0	-2.059	-.608	***
educm_2	-.352	.095	-3.73	0	-.538	-.167	***
educm_3	-.009	.162	-0.06	.956	-.326	.308	
educm_4	-.281	.215	-1.31	.19	-.702	.139	
educm_5	.135	.392	0.34	.731	-.633	.903	
relig_1	.153	1.103	0.14	.889	-2.008	2.315	
relig_2	.859	1.226	0.70	.484	-1.544	3.261	
relig_3	-.227	1.107	-0.20	.838	-2.397	1.943	
relig_4	.922	1.1	0.84	.402	-1.234	3.079	
relig_5	.545	1.253	0.44	.663	-1.911	3.002	
Constant	-4.401	1.111	-3.96	0	-6.578	-2.224	***
Mean dependent var		0.115	SD dependent var			0.319	
Pseudo r-squared		0.377	Number of obs			9824	
Chi-square		2643.686	Prob > chi2			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		4408.464	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			4566.700	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

5.5. Egypt (2008-2014) and Ethiopia (2005-2016):

In the following regression, we combined the four previous databases to obtain an overview of the determinants of FGC and to analyse the impact of the country of residence and the year on the evolution of women's position on FGC.

What the results of this regression tell us is that the probability that a woman living in Egypt wants the practice to continue is 148 percentage points higher than if she lives in Ethiopia. This is not surprising because we can see in the review of literature or stylized facts that women living in Egypt are more circumcised and want the practice to continue. This suggests that female circumcision is a practice that is more deeply rooted in Egyptian customs and traditions than in Ethiopia.

Besides, we note that in 2005 and 2008, the probability that women think that circumcision should continue is 34% higher than in 2014 and 2016. This suggests that over time women are becoming less supportive of this practice. It is likely that over the years this practice will gradually disappear naturally.

Table 5 - Logit model: Egypt (2008 and 2014) and Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

Logistic regression							
circont	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Intervall]	Sig
Egypt	1.482	.02	75.63	0	1.443	1.52	***
Year2010	.34	.018	18.99	0	.305	.375	***
Constant	-1.276	.02	-64.15	0	-1.315	-1.237	***
Mean dependent var		0.472	SD dependent var			0.499	
Pseudo r-squared		0.078	Number of obs			58772	
Chi-square		6359.065	Prob > chi2			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		74936.162	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			74963.107	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

5.6. Interpretations :

The probability that a woman who has been circumcised will perform FGC on her daughter is more than 200 times greater than the probability that a woman who has not been circumcised will do so. This validates what has been said in the review literature: a circumcised woman is much more likely to support the practice than a woman who is not. It suggests that it is a practice that stems from culture and tradition. You don't question something that is so deeply rooted. The fact that the probability of a woman living in Egypt supporting this practice is much higher than that of a woman living in Ethiopia shows that the country's traditions and culture are a determinant of FGC. Thus, in Egypt the traditions seem to be more favorable to this practice.

This could also be explained by religion, as we know that in Egypt the majority of the population is Muslim. It seems that women of the Muslim religion would like more than those of the "other" religion to maintain the practice of excision. Religion, therefore, seems to be a determinant of this practice but in this article there is too little evidence of this. The variables that concern religion are not very often significant, which leads to the fact that we cannot conclude anything about religion.

However, whether in Ethiopia or Egypt, the likelihood that a circumcised woman will support the practice decreases over time. It seems that fewer and fewer of them believe that cutting should continue.

This can be explained by the fact that over the years, educated women in Egypt and Ethiopia have become less and less willing to continue cutting. Nowadays, the harms of FGC are increasingly being shown and exposed. Educated women can easily obtain information about it. This can easily be a factor in the decrease in the likelihood of women wanting the practice to continue, as well as in the education of their husbands. If men change their minds about their position on FGC, it will influence their wives, and may also affect the opinions of even uneducated women. There are more and more educated women and men in Egypt and Ethiopia, which can explain this decrease.

In addition, we noticed that women who do not work want this practice to continue, on average, more than women who do have a job. This indicates that reducing inequalities in access to the labor market would increase the chances of reducing the practice. All gender inequalities would therefore be linked, and launching a policy that aims to reduce them (whether, for example, just in the labor market) can lead to a virtuous circle of decreasing gender inequalities that are harmful to society or to the country's development.

Women living in urban areas are less likely to tolerate FGC, but especially in governorates such as Cairo. This indicates that in the city, women question their traditions more than women living in the same environment and with the same entourage all their lives. Facilitating mobility and access to life could help limit this practice. However, there is little difference in the position on FGC between women living in urban and rural areas.

Some factors that have an impact on FGC are promising. In addition, women surveyed before 2010, on average, want this practice to continue more than women surveyed after 2010, which

is in the same direction. This indicates that FGM/C is becoming more questioned and less entrenched in traditions. We can assume that over time, even if no efforts are made (that is, no policy or program that fights against excision is launched) in Egypt and Ethiopia, this practice may disappear, or at least significantly reduce.

Finally, we notice that this practice is more anchored in the Egyptian traditions than in the Ethiopian.

One of the limitations of our model concerns the determinant of the woman's age. In the model for women in Egypt in 2008, the results are not surprising because younger women seem to be less likely to think that this practice should continue. In Ethiopia, it appears that younger women are more likely to want the practice to continue, compared to older women. However, we have seen, thanks to tables created from the databases, that the older the women are, the more they want FGC to continue. It is difficult for us to draw a conclusion, knowing that even in Egypt, the variables concerning age are not significant in 2014. However, we can think that younger women seem to support this practice less than older ones. This would indicate that, over time, the practice may decrease and, in the long run, disappear.

We note that in all our regressions the R squares are not high, indicating that the model explains weakly the variations of the dependent variable. This could mean that the dependent variables are not really determinants of FGC. However, these are logit models, whose R squares are always low.

6. Conclusion :

This paper empirically investigates the determinants of FGC in Egypt and Ethiopia from 2005 to 2016. A logit model is used to estimate these determinants. For this purpose, the dependent variable used is the women's willingness to continue the practice or not, which allows us to analyze the determinants of this practice in the long run. This variable is equal to 1 if the woman wants the practice to continue and 0 otherwise. In terms of results, most of the coefficients are significant, except for a few that we cannot interpret. We find that the fact that the woman has been excised or not has the most impact on the woman's opinion. The environment in which she lives also has an impact on her opinion on this subject. We find a negative correlation between her level of education and that of her husband. Logically, the fact that she does not have a job increases the perpetuity of this practice. We cannot conclude anything about the age whose results are very surprising, but it appears that the older the women, the more they want FGC to continue, which is promising for the future.

It is promising to see that women interviewed after 2010 are less interested in continuing the practice than those interviewed before 2010.

It is therefore possible that time will diminish this practice, but it requires a lot of it. In order for this practice to disappear as soon as possible, campaigns can be tried. In the existing literature, three possible types of campaigns were identified, based on the decrease of footbinding in China. In order to eliminate it, the authorities first educated the population by telling them that in the rest of the world footbinding was a denounced practice. Then they

explained the disadvantages of this practice and the benefits of not doing it. Finally, they formed "natural foot societies" that committed themselves not to allow their sons to marry women with binded feet, and/or not to allow their daughters to do so (Mackie and LeJeune (2009)). Thus, when we apply this situation to that of female circumcision, we can deduce possible solutions. One possible campaign is the increase of education, and employment, which could help the emancipation of women and decrease patriarchal ideas. In addition, as highlighting the negative impacts on women's health would be a factor in reducing FGM/C, showing the costs of this practice could help people understand that the benefits are lower (Gulesci et al. (2021)). Since cutting girls comes from the parents' desire to bring well-being to their child (to fight against their exclusion from society), knowing the costs, at least in terms of health, for their daughter could make them question this act. To finish, the creation of associations of parents who fight against excision can reduce this practice. They would commit to not cutting their daughters, or to not marrying their sons to a woman who has been cut (Mackie (1996)). Some articles have also identified which policies are ineffective. Sanctions and convictions would not reduce FGM/C, and on the contrary would lead to more deaths due to it, because it would be performed in more dangerous places and that this could lead to more serious consequences, such as death (Freymeyer and Johnson (2007)).

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Appendix:

Table 6: Distribution of women according to their opinion about circumcision and their age – Ethiopia 2005

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)

Table 7: Distribution of women according to their opinion about circumcision and their age – Ethiopia 2016

Source: Constructed by the author based on DHS dataset in Ethiopia (2005 and 2016)